

WAYS TO IMPROVE INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN PUBLIC EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ta'lim muassasalarida inklyuziv ta'lim tizimini takomillashtirish, ota-onalar va maktab xodimlari uchun inklyuziv ta'limni takomillashtirish va uni ta'lim jarayoniga tadbiq etish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida ma'lumotlar berilgan, uzluksiz ta'lim tizimiga jalb qilish uchun maxsus ehtiyojlarga muhtoj bolalar uchun metodik ko'nikma va tavsiyalar bayon etilgan.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о внедрении системы инклюзивного образования в школах, мерах по совершенствованию инклюзивного образования родителей и сотрудников школы и его применению в образовательном процессе, а также методические указания и рекомендации по привлечению детей, нуждающихся в специальном образовании, в систему непрерывного образования.

Annotatation: This article provides information on the implementation of an inclusive education system in schools, measures to improve inclusive education for parents and school staff and apply it to the teaching process, and outlines methodological skills and recommendations for children in need of special needs to be attracted to a continuous education system.

Kalit soʻzlar: intellektual ta'lim, imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar, maktab, huquq, tarbiya, tarbiya, nuqson, natijalar, amaliyot, mutaxassislik, o'qituvchi, metod, maqsad, vazifa, segregatsiya.

Ключевые слова: интеллектуальное воспитание, дети с ограниченными возможностями здоровья, школа, образование, воспитание, дефект, результаты, практика, специальность, педагог, метод, цель, воспитание, сегрегация.

Keywords: Inclusive education, children with disabilities, school, law, upbringing, defect, result, practice, special, pedagogical, method, goal, task, segregation.

In recent years, a number of measures have been taken around the world to enrol students in public schools and preschool children in educational institutions. Work is underway to prepare children for a full life and to equip them with the necessary knowledge, skills and skills. Today it is clear to everyone how important school and preschool education are. Therefore, the proper education of preschool children is one of the most important issues. Work is carried out to get children out of the speech impasse, work on their cognitive processes, develop knowledge, skills and skills. Until the end of the school year, education is aimed at the formation of a physically healthy and spiritually mature personality of the child, as well as preparing him for school. Article 11 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" states: "This education is carried out in the family, kindergarten and other educational institutions, regardless of their form of ownership, at the age of 6 to 7 years." The Ministry of Public Education of UNICEF decided to develop draft normative acts on the role of specialized teachers and psychologists in inclusive education, as a result of which strategies were developed, which will quickly and effectively lead to the development of specialized and specialized education for children in need of a place in public life. Under the auspices of UNICEF, a five-year plan of work on inclusive education has been integrated into the overall plan of the education sector and implemented in all parts of education for its implementation. To help those who want to benefit the worldwide work of Jehovah's Witnesses, a brochure has been prepared under the title "A Blessed Plan of Serving the Church Worldwide." It consists in the implementation of programs as an experience in Uzbekistan under the auspices of the Special Olympics. In recent years, our country has been paying special attention to a number of issues, such as improving the educational process of settlement, expanding the scope of services provided to them, attracting the population to higher education, attracting not only higher education, but also children to preschool education."

Regardless of the abilities and condition of the children, it is necessary to give quality education to all of them.

The issue of raising children with disabilities is now one of the most important. At present, a system of inclusive education is being introduced in order to implement training in the system of special or general education based on the level, capabilities, characteristics and abilities of children in need of special assistance in the country. An inclusive culture of education is seen as evidence that affirms and endorses the reform of each student's property in accordance with the Salama Declaration. Its purpose is not to prevent social segregation because of differences in gender, religion, culture, social ethnic affiliation, religion, individual abilities and abilities, but to prevent the widespread use of this concept. In accordance with world experience, the incorporation into schools is often considered as the education of invalids in secondary schools, along with peers. Recently, the prospects for inclusive education have aroused great interest not only among the organizers of the educational process, but also among parents raising children with disabilities. Today, the question of how the problems with the joint education of "special" and ordinary children are solved not only in Russia, but also in foreign countries, is especially relevant. Inclusive education, first of all, involves the creation of optimal conditions for all its participants to receive knowledge. Specialists in educational education, psychologists, speech therapists and others solve issues related to the learning process. But the difficulties of the "special" child and his family, most of all, remain their difficulties. Without solutions, they can lead to the fact that such a student will be forced out of the educational environment and the children's community. As a result, each participant in such an incorporation may call himself an aggrieved party. It is well known that the effectiveness of raising and educating children is determined directly by the level of socio-psychological adaptation of parents, that is, by their own characteristics of the development of their children, the main characteristics of the quality of mental development and their compliance with young standards and an emotionally positive sense of guilt before the child, embarrassment in front of others, a bad influence on the parents, and the child's sense of negligence on the whole. For

such parents, it is important to be able to maintain constant contact with people who have faced such difficulties in their personal experience and to be able to learn not only to live with these problems, but also to deal with them. It is the parents of "special" children who demand that they join a normal children's community. First of all, the social adaptation of this "unique" child in real life is due to the fact that a well-developed correction (correction) is supported by the method of teaching children with decades of developmental problems in the education system, detached from society. Children are better adapted to life in general education schools than in institutions specializing in special needs, especially in the acquisition of social experience. Healthy children improve their educational abilities, develop tolerance, activity and self-sufficiency. In this process, the role of teachers and specialized pedagogues is important, who bring their experience and knowledge so that each child learns with the greatest benefit for himself. An inclusive approach means that teachers provide individual support to all students, but some groups of students remain indistinguishable from others.

It is worth noting that the problem of inclusive education is complex, multidimensional and contains many components. Providing not only an effective, but also an economical method of developing the education of children with disabilities, it is necessary to emphasize the social barriers and organizational challenges called by an unhindered environment in the absence of popular prejudices and pedagogical stereotypes. It is necessary to study public opinion on the problems of education, the opinion of schoolchildren, their parents, teachers about the advantages and disadvantages of educating children with disabilities in a joint educational environment with ordinary children. The organization of inclusive education presupposes the creation of certain conditions. Thus, the majority of parents and teachers believe that a pedagogue-psychologist (79% of parents and 92% of teachers) and a special pedagogue (46% of parents and 84% of teachers) are needed to teach pupils with developmental and health problems together with a teacher. Teachers suggest that physiologists and neurologists from among medical experts should be involved in this process. Schools conduct psychological trainings

for parents in order to increase their ability to raise and communicate with children (53% of surveyed parents) and psychological consultations (56% of surveyed parents). In a modern school of a new type, education, and not education, is adapted to the capabilities of the child. Inclusive education can only achieve effective results when all participants work within the target framework. Who are these participants? These include family, neighbors, school staff, classmates, healthy students, specialists, pedagogues, psychologists, medical workers, speech therapists-defectors, as well as the health care system, the system of native education, medical, pedagogical and psychological commissions.

In conclusion, if children with disabilities are involved in inclusive education at a young age; to communicate with others and peers, to learn to serve oneself, to be ready for school education. Now he is ready to study, work, participate in various relationships as a citizen. Parents and loved ones do not get into the air from his exit. Those who know and know who he is and what he is capable of believe in him. As a result, he will be able to create a family and feed the family. When children with disabilities study with the same people as they are in a special school for 10-12 years, their communication with healthy people is severely limited. Most parents try to feed at home in order to wake up. Cause: The child does not have the self-confidence to work or enter into other relationships with healthy people. They also experience the fact that others treat their child in a negative way. Methodological recommendations to strengthen the responsibility of families by working in cooperation with parents to direct children with disabilities to inclusive education, helping them to enter school, monitoring them during the examination, providing them with the necessary teaching aids, preparing lessons at home, regularly monitoring the general development, educating the child and taking the necessary measures.

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